

COST AND WEIGHT EFFICIENT ASSEMBLY OF AERONAUTICAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials and integrated structures are weight-efficient, but not necessarily cost-efficient. In order to compare weight benefits with production cost penalties, the influence of each must be studied simultaneously. Production costs are challenging to estimate as they depend on production method choice as well as involved process variables such as annual production volume. In order to enable simultaneous analysis of cost and weight it is therefore necessary to develop tools that assist in production cost estimation. This paper presents the continuation of previous work, where the manufacturing costs of a composite structure is studied using a novel cost estimation tool, here extended to include that of assembly costs. Focus of this paper is assembly of aeronautical structures. The model is finally applied and discussed through estimating the assembly costs of two cases; that of a co-cured structure and that of a mechanically joined structure.

The case study shows that the co-cured wing box is more cost-efficient than that of the mechanically joined wing box. Regarding weight, the mechanically joined structure increases the structural weight by about 1 kg, which corresponds to a weight increase of 1 %. Important cost drivers for the mechanically joined wing box are fastening, drilling and shimming costs, each representing about 20 % of the total cost as the annual production volume increases to 1000 produced structures per year. Important cost drivers for the co-cured wing box is the cost of part positioning and autoclave curing, representing about 40 % of the total cost each as the annual production volume increases to 1000 produced structures per year.

1 INTRODUCTION

Low structural weight is vital in aeronautical adaptations in order to curb CO₂ emissions, reach set environmental targets [1] and reduce continuous running costs. To achieve low structural weight lightweight materials and integrated structures, which decrease the number of weighty joints used, are favoured. To that end, composite materials, with their low density, high specific strength and integration possibilities are frequently used. The actual manufacture and assembly of full composite structures is however challenging, and thereby also costly.

The assembly of a composite structure is particularly challenging due to the fact that individual properties of the composite constituents must be considered simultaneously during secondary processing such as drilling, fixturing and application and curing of adhesives. In addition, the assembly of a composite structure must also compensate for previous manufacturing deviations through introduction of shimming or pre-design of sacrificial layers. Both methods increase the cost of the assembly of the structure, through sometimes radically increased production time and pure material waste cost. These production considerations make it clear that although composite structures can be highly weight efficient, they may not be cost efficient.

To properly address both weight, and thereby environmental sustainability, together with production cost concerns, the trade-off between weight and cost of a composite structure should be studied simultaneously. Research regarding cost and weight of individual composite parts includes multi-objective optimization studies [2] and different cost estimation strategies [3-5]. Previous work by the authors [6] complements these by developing a flexible composite cost estimation model, able to evaluate generic co-cured structures with respect to common aeronautical manufacturing methods

of different levels of automation. However, this model does not include assembly costs, the addition of these costs to previous model are the focus of present paper.. The implementation of assembly costs is especially important when discussing the value of integration related to cost.

The developed tool provides the basis needed in order to discuss the trade-off between weight and cost of composite structures, throughout the full production chain from part manufacture to assembly. As with previous work, the focus of the study within this paper is aeronautical structures. The paper briefly introduces extended cost model [6], with details regarding used assembly method. Finally a case study in which the model is used in order to evaluate the joining of a generic wing box is presented. The case study is a cost and weight comparison of a co-cured versus a mechanically joined wing box.

2 COMPOSITE COST MODEL

The cost of a generic composite structure consists of the manufacturing costs of the individual parts and the assembly cost of the whole structure. Current paper is based on the continuation of previous work [6], where a modular cost estimation methodology is proposed. The methodology is based on a bottom-up approach, where the production and its cost is constructed from combining included process steps that defines necessary investment, operator, tooling, floor and electricity costs. The method is modular in that the defined process steps are easily modified to fit sough production method. This means that the construction of a new production study is simply a matter of rearranging process steps with new input data. This also means that the extension of previous work [6], that focused on manufacture, to include assembly is freely adoptable through defining some new process steps while reusing some. Costs due to product development, testing and certification are not within the scope of the paper. Furthermore, inspection costs, NDT and DT, are also excluded from current work as this is basis for future work.

3 ASSEMBLY PROCESS

The aeronautical assembly processes studied in this paper are first that of mechanical joining and second that of co-curing. The latter produces a single, co-cured part and its cost could therefore be considered to be pure part cost, rather than assembly cost. However, for the sake of comparison, added costs due to mounting and curing of co-curing parts are studied as pure assembly costs in this paper. Important to note is also that the cost of the curing mould is here considered to be a cost carried by the part manufacture cost and not the assembly cost, as it is assumed that used layup-mould will be re-used for the curing stage.

The mechanical joining of a composite structure within aerospace includes many steps, see Figure 1. The steps involved can be divided into several sub-groups according to: positioning, shimming, tack, deburring and cleaning, drilling and fastening. These sub-groups are further described in appropriate section following below.

Figure 1: Generic process cycle for the mechanical joining of a part to another.

The process of co-curing a composite structure is schematically shorter than that of mechanical joining, but it is not less complex, see Figure 2. The process consists of individual positioning of wet parts, bagging of full structure and finally, curing of full structure in an autoclave.

Figure 2: Generic process cycle for the co-curing of a structure.

The processes described above are further explained in the following subsections.

3.1 Loading and positioning

Positioning can be done either manually or semi-manual. To the authors' knowledge, no system within the aerospace industry available today is able to fully automatize the positioning process. Rather, semi-manual, in which operators utilize assisting equipment which lift, measure or guides the positioning, is most common today. Assisting systems used include ceiling cranes [7] and manual measuring tools. The positioning process considered herein is traditional and only include the costs as a result of operators with assisting ceiling crane if the part to be moved is larger than 1 m². Considered ceiling crane cost 1 M€ [7]. Cycle time is a function of part size and positioning complexity. In this case the positioning of a part is considered to take 10 min. Another important cost related to positioning is used assembly jigs. Considered jig cost is 38 k€ [8]. Loading and positioning of wet parts, such as in studied case of co-curing, must however be carried out fully manually, and assisting cranes are not used. In this scenario a simpler guiding jig, which need not be as robust as that of a jig to be used during drilling, of about 30% lower cost is used.

3.2 Shimming

Shimming is a major cost when working with composite parts; some estimate the cost to represent 20 % of the assembly cost. The shimming also governs possible station rate of an assembly due to required long curing time of the adhesion of a fixed shim or added liquid shim. The considered shimming process follows the abbreviated process described in Figure 1. Shimming cost within this paper correspond to the curing time of a liquid shim of a curing cycle of 3 hours. It is assumed that the shim can be cured at room temperature.

3.3 Drilling

Drilling is a vital step. Drilling is often carried out using large robotic cells. However, not all holes can be drilled automatically, which means a certain percentage will have to be drilled manually at a considerable cycle time increase and thereby also cost increase. A robotic drilling cell cost in the region of 1-1.5 M€ [8], here necessary drilling cell is considered to cost 1 M€. The drilling speed can be reflected in drilled holes per minute. A drilling speed of 4 holes per minute has been reported [9], but in studied scenario, a conservative estimate of a drilling speed of 2 holes per minute is assumed.

3.3.1 The mechanical joint

In order to calculate the cost of a mechanically fastened joint, an approximate number of fasteners used must be estimated. Bolted joints are of either single row or multi-row design. In general, secondary joints are designed as the former while primary bonds need a multi-row setup [10] For composite parts of single row joints a pitch distance of 4D-5D, where D is the hole diameter, is often used [11-12].

3.4 Deburring and cleaning

When holes are drilled, they must be deburred and cleaned. To do this the parts that have been drilled must be taken apart. Some drilling processes such as orbital drilling [13] potentially allow for burr-free drilling, thus eliminating the necessity to repeatedly mount and dismount parts. However, deburring can in general not be removed completely. The deburring process on composite materials in aerospace is often carried out by hand [14-15], while automated processes can be found when working with metals within for example the automotive industry [16]. The manual deburring process either use slow-speed die grinders, hand-held pneumatic tools which rotates a drill bit within drilled hole, or, more commonly in sensitive cases, a simple burring tool which is rotated by hand within drilled hole [17]. In this case it is assumed that the deburring process is sensitive, and is therefore carried out using a simple burring tool, and that the deburring time of one hole takes approximately 5 minutes [18]. The cost of a deburring tool is not high, but the tool needs to be exchanged regularly. This means there is a reinvestment cost after a certain number of holes or parts deburred. However, due to the low cost of one tool, this cost is disregarded. General cleaning is also necessary, it is assumed that 10 minutes of operator time is needed per m² surface cleaned. Important costs due to deburring and cleaning relate to used operator time.

3.5 Fastening

Temporary and final fasteners are used in a general assembly. Temporary fasteners are added throughout the assembly process in order to support the structure enough to be able to measure, shim and drill parts relative to each other. Temporary fasteners are removed and final fasteners are placed before the full assembly is complete.

There are several automatic fastening systems available, tailored to specific assembly types such as wings [19], fuselage sections [20-21], and some more flexible systems which include spar and wing box fastener cells [19] and the novel snake-arm robot for hard to reach areas [22]. However, as the latter is not currently employed in production there is a lack of flexible automation solutions for both smaller assemblies and lower annual volume productions. Simple curvatures can potentially make use of regular industrial robots, however due to the high tolerance requirements and required repeatability coupled with flexibility demands within aeronautics, industry robots can sometimes not meet put demands. In these scenarios manual fastening is still the dominant method [23]. To that end, manual fastening is primarily considered in the case study within this paper.

The manual process consists of identifying holes and adding the fastener. The fastener is added with the help of a fastener gun, which generally is tailored to the fastener to be added. The cost of a fastening gun depend on choice of fasteners, in this case a simple pneumatic-hydraulic gun of approximate cost 500 € is considered [24]. The fastener itself must be adapted to composite materials, and as such they are often more expensive than their metal counterparts and could cost up to 10 € á piece. Fasteners are often made of titanium and can be installed from both sides, or in one-shot through blind fasteners. Here Accu-Lok® 4.178 mm blind fastener of Titanium 6Al-4V is considered to be used [25]. Each is considered to weigh approximately 2g.

3.6 Bagging

A part that is to be cured must first be properly bagged in order to allow for a correct cured shape. The quality of the bag highly affects the final part quality [26]. In this scenario, the bagging effort is considered to correspond to half the time of the total part curing time. The cost of the bagging stage is considered to be equal to necessary cost of the operator.

3.7 Co-curing

The curing of a part is within aerospace most frequently carried out using an appropriate curing cycle within an autoclave, rather than an oven, in order to achieve necessary final part quality. Autoclave curing costs are calculated as given in [6], with a curing time of 3 hours used.

4 CASE STUDY

Considered case is a comparison between two approaches, the first is a co-cured structure and the second is a mechanically joined structure. The considered wing box cover is shown in Figure 3. As is visible the wing box contains a base cover, stiffeners and rib feet. In the first scenario, the base cover, stiffeners and rib feet are manufactured wet, positioned and allowed to co-cure. This results in an integrated part of a certain weight. In the second scenario, the base cover, stiffeners and rib feet are manufactured, cured and then mechanically joined using composite fasteners. The fasteners add to the overall weight of the structure.

Figure 3: Studied wing box cover containing longitude stiffeners and rib feet.

4.1 Results

The assembly cost decreases with increasing production volume, as given in Figure 4. Peaks on the curves represent a re-investment cost, either that of a new jig or a new piece of equipment. At a certain production volume a stable cost is reached, at which depreciation rates of investments and tooling costs no longer affect the overall cost per structure. In these cases, the cost can be considered to have reached its stable cost at about an annual manufacturing volume of 2000 structures per year.

Figure 4: The assembly cost decreases with increasing annual manufacturing volume.

4.2 Detailed contributions with respect to cost category

Detailed costs are given in Figure 5 for mechanical joints and co-curing. The cost of the mechanical joining is dominated by accessories, operating and investment costs. The accessory, or

used fasteners cost, is a result of using a pitch distance of 4D with a hole size of 4.178 mm, which gives an approximate number of holes per studied structure of 434 where each used fastener cost 1 €. The added weight due to the used fasteners is low, with a total weight of about 1 kg. The cost of a co-cured structure is initially dominated by investment costs, and at higher annual production volumes; operating and power consumption costs become more important.

Figure 5: Detailed cost results for a) mechanical joining and b) co-cured structure.

The cost is a sum of each involved process, detailed cost per process is for both cases given in Figure 6. Cost per process for mechanical joining, fastening, drilling and shimming cost contribute the most to the overall cost while the cost of part positioning and deburring and cleaning come next in order of magnitude. Cost per process for a co-cured structure are dominated by the autoclave cost, while for higher annual production volumes, the cost of part positioning is the dominating cost.

Figure 6: Cost per assembly process for a) mechanical joining and b) co-cured structure. Note that in a) the fastening cost includes that of used fasteners.

5 DISCUSSIONS

The modular cost model presented within this paper is shown to reflect assembly costs of a generic aeronautical structure. The resulting cost analysis is a direct result of considered assembly. The process parameters used are highly variable depending on production scenario which means costs given within this paper simply represent one possible one. With this in mind it is in this scenario clear that the cost of a co-cured structure is low with respect to its assembly cost. A point to note in this case is that the co-curing jig cost used in this analysis could very well be higher in reality if special solutions, such as a rotation from convex to concave curing mould, is required. Nevertheless, the assembly cost difference is substantial between the two options, leaving room for a higher jig cost.

Another important cost with regards to the cost difference between the two cases is that of inspection cost. The addition of inspection cost may alter the final conclusion, under the assumption that inspection is even possible for the co-cured structure.

The cost of the mechanically joined structure is shown to be dominated by the cost of fastening, shimming and drilling. The high cost of fastening and drilling motivate the reduction of number of fasteners used. The introduction of adhesive joints could potentially improve the overall cost.

The cost of the co-cured structure is shown to be initially dominated by the autoclave investment cost, at higher annual production volumes the importance of part positioning on the cost grows.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The modular cost model presented within this paper is shown to reflect assembly costs of a generic aeronautical structure. Studied assembly processes are the basis for the following set of conclusions:

- The co-cured wing box represents the lowest cost production option
- The cost of fastening and drilling for a composite mechanical joint design is high
- Shimming represent a substantial cost which do not decrease with increasing production volume

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Quentin and J. Szodruch, *2008 Addendum to the strategic research agenda*, Advisory council for aviation research and innovation in Europe (ACARE), 2008.
- [2] M. Kaufmann and D. Zenkert and M. Åkermo, Material Selection for a Curved C-Spar Based on Cost Optimization, *Journal of Aircraft*, **48**, 2011, pp. 797-804 (doi: [10.2514/1.C000188](https://doi.org/10.2514/1.C000188)).
- [3] M. Åkermo and B.T. Åström, Modelling component cost in compression moulding of thermoplastic composite and sandwich components, *Composites Part A*, **31**, 1999, pp. 319-333 (doi: [10.1016/S1359-835X\(99\)00079-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(99)00079-2)).
- [4] R. Curran and A. Rothwell and S. Castagne, Numerical method for cost-weight optimization of stringer-skin panels, *Journal of Aircraft*, **43**, 2006, pp. 264-274 (doi: [10.2514/1.13225](https://doi.org/10.2514/1.13225)).
- [5] P.J. Schubel, Cost modelling in polymer composite applications: Case study - Analysis of existing and automated manufacturing processes for a large wind turbine blade, *Composites Part B*, **43**, 2012, pp. 953 – 960 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.11.036](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.11.036)).
- [6] M.K. Hagnell and M. Åkermo, A composite cost model for the aeronautical industry: methodology and case study, accepted to *Composites Part B* (in press), (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.04.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.04.043)).
- [7] T. Morgan, Personal communication, RHC Lifting Limited, 2014-10-03.
- [8] G.F. Barbosa and J. Carvalho, Analytical model for aircraft design based on Design for Excellence (DFX) concepts and use of composite material oriented to automated processes, *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, **69**, 2013, pp. 2333-2342 (doi: [10.1007/s00170-013-5211-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-013-5211-7)).
- [9] Y.Yao, Design and experiment of a robot automatic drilling system, *Proceedings of the SAE 2014 Aerospace Manufacturing and Automated Fastening Conference and Exhibition, Salt Lake City, USA, September 23-25, 2014*, SAE Technical papers (doi: [10.4271/2014-01-2246](https://doi.org/10.4271/2014-01-2246)).
- [10] *Military Handbook - MIL-HDBK-17-3F: Composite Materials Handbook - Polymer Matrix Composites Materials Usage, Design, and Analysis*, Vol 3, U.S. Department of Defence, 2002.
- [11] E. Hörberg, Personal communication, Saab Aeronautics, 2014.
- [12] A.S. Mosallam, *Design Guide for FRP Composite Connections*, American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE), Reston, 2011.

- [13] F. Latger, T. Harris and S. Björklund, Drilling cost model, *Proceedings of the 2002 SAE Aerospace Automated Fastening Conference and Exhibition*, SAE Technical Papers (10.4271/2002-01-2632).
- [14] A. Höglund, Personal communication, Saab Aeronautics, 2013-10-17.
- [15] F.C. Campbell, *Manufacturing Technology for Aerospace Structural Materials*, Elsevier Science, 2006.
- [16] B-S. Ryuh and G. R. Pennock, *Industrial Robotics: Programming, Simulation and Applications - Robot Automation systems for deburring* (Ed. L.K. Huat), Pro literatur verlag, 2006.
- [17] Federal aviation administration, *Aviation maintenance technician handbook - airframe, volume 1 (FAA-H-8083-31)*, US Department of Transportation - Federal aviation administration, Airman testing standards branch, 2012.
- [18] L.K. Gillespie, *Hand deburring: Increasing shop productivity*, Society of Manufacturing Engineers (SME), 2003.
- [19] Gemcor, Wing fastening systems, www.gemcor.com/wp/automation-products/wing-fastening-systems/, last retrieved 2015-04-15.
- [20] E. Stansbury, B. Bigoney and R. Allen, E7000 High-speed CNC fuselage riveting cell, *SAE International Journal of Materials and Manufacturing*, **1**, 2014, pp. 37-44 (doi: [10.4271/2013-01-2150](https://doi.org/10.4271/2013-01-2150)).
- [21] ElectroImpact, Automated Fastening, www.electroimpact.com/Products/Fastening/E7000.aspx, last retrieved 2015-04-15.
- [22] R. Buckingham, V. Chitrakaran, R. Conkie et al., Snake-Arm Robots: A New Approach to Aircraft Assembly, *Proceedings of Aerospace Technology Conference and Exposition 2007*, SAE Technical Paper series (doi: [10.4271/2007-01-3870](https://doi.org/10.4271/2007-01-3870)).
- [23] J. Camillo, Aerospace fastening in the 21st century, *Assembly*, 2012.
- [24] Aircraft Spruce & specialty co., Pneumatic-hydraulic blind riveter, <http://www.aircraft-spruce.com/catalog/topages/heavydutyriv.php?clickkey=7294>, last retrieved 2015-04-15.
- [25] ALCOA Fastening Systems & Rings Aerospace, Accu-Lok® Blind Fastening System, http://www.alcoa.com/fastening_systems_and_rings/aerospace/en/product.asp?cat_id=659&prod_id=457, last retrieved 2015-04-15.
- [26] M. Peterssen, Personal communication, Saab Aeronautics, 2015.